
WEB BASED LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract:

World Wide Web (WWW) and Internet as a new media of information storage and delivery provides supreme media for delivery of information with greater speed. As more libraries move towards providing their services in a digital environment. Web based library services, why it is necessary and attractive among users.

Keywords: *WWW., Web based library services, Online information Services*

Introduction:

Web base information and communication Technologies (ICT) and globalization of networks and exponential rise of new information and the use of traditional tools in information management have been reduced and automation of information centre has become imperative. Web based library services refer to facilities, which are provided by a library for the use of books and dissemination of information for the need and meet the user's requirement. The well known existing library services are cataloguing, classification, circulation services, CAS, SDI, new arrivals, current content inter library loan, externally purchased database, Internally published newsletters, reports and journal, bibliographic services and so on.

Web Based Library Services:

At beginning library was just a store house of books and other document. General people were not allowed to use that document. After long time library

started document delivery service and circulation came into picture

Advantages of Web Based Services:

- To save the precious time of the scientist and users
- Availability of less number of library staff to carry out the library works and services
- less dependence upon the library staff for getting the required information
- Instant and elaborate information requirements of R&D activities
- Information for decision making in MIS
- Multifold increase of the cost of books and journals
- Availability of information in different places and also in different campus

Scope of Web based Service:

Online and ordering and acquisition related activities can be carried out through e-mail Centralization and computerized on line public access cataloguing service can be provided by networking system. Networking CD-ROM

and multimedia service can be provided effectively through networks. Current Awareness service and SDI may be given through networking system and the users may retrieve reference of their interest in fact of second from online database. The internet with union catalogue of various items of information is a boon as it avoids duplications in holding to the extent possible. Reference service can be enhanced by e-mail and internet through LAN and WAN.

General Services Offered By Web:

Following are the very common and general services offer by web Some of them we can apply on our library and information science field.

- List serve
- Subject database
- Community information
- Government resources
- Library catalogue
- Bibliographic and Cataloguing Service
- Current Awareness Services
- Electronic Selective Dissemination of Information
- Document delivery
- Commercial resource
- Bulletin board E-mail facilities
- Surfing facilities Internet subject Gateway
- News Clipping Services
- News Group Newsletter services

Special Services offered by Web:

1. Patent Information Services:

Internet is the fastest expanding network to access patent information source of different countries most important patent information service available on internet are

- General information for obtaining patent(full text or bibliography),list of publications, and offices like USPTO, IP office of Brazil, and Canadian

patents and current awareness services from bibliographic database. Trademark office (USPTO) allows access to their patent databases(<http://www.uspto.gov>)

- Search can be made by invests name, applicant's name, Classification symbols etc. It is free access service for the users, (<http://patents.cnidr.org>) Full text of patent are not available for free service through Internet. US patent.
- Derwent's Scientific and patent Information(<http://www.derwent.co.uk/>)Derwent World patent index contains Derwent's database is available different online hosts like DIALOG. STN, datastar, Other etc. They are giving likes to other various patent information services.
- Biotechnology Patents: (<http://www.inform.umd.edu:8080/Ed/Res/Topic/AgrEnv/Biotech?Biotechp> patent.
- Chemical patents plus from Chemical Abstracts(<http://casweb.cas.org/chempat> plus/ new patent files can also be free of cost

2. Reference Services:

The reference service in a library is often defined as direct personal assistance given to its reader for finding information . It is the branch of library services. Which includes personal assistance given to in their search for information on various subject areas, irrespective of size and collection of the library. Whereas much of traditional library networking has focused on information access within and between physical boundaries of libraries and research institutions. The goal is to meet the demand for easy 24 hours access to electronic reference sources from the dorm room, the office, and even the kitchen table, Virtually every academic library and

almost all public ones offer access to CDROM Products. Almost all-academic libraries offer mediated access to traditional online service such as DIALOG.

3. Uncover:

Uncover is an online periodical article delivery service and current awareness alerting service, It indexed nearly 18000 English language periodicals in its database and is still growing. Over eight million articles are available through a simple online order system. Five thousand citations are added daily. Articles appear in Uncover at the same time the periodical issue is delivered to your library or local newsstand, which makes uncover the most up-to-date index anywhere, It is very helpful to the people who need up-to the minute information, delivered quickly. Articles locked in the Uncover database can be sent via fax machine within 24-48 hours, Monday to Friday-often in less than one hours. Searching the Uncover database is absolutely free.

4. Web Casting:

Webcasting which is another example of push Technology is defined as the "Pre-Arranged updating of news, Weather or other selected information on an Internet user's desktop through periodic and generally unobtrusive over the WWW". In other words, push technology or webcasting is a method of information delivery across the web that pushes information to the screens of user's computer. It is a webcasting was introduced by the point cast Network in 1996. Presently most of the webcasters concentrate on news delivery.

5. White Board Environment:

In the Environment, there can be many users connected to discuss on a topic and it is isotopic and its is different from the new group in the sense that the computer screen serves as whiteboard and

the user can draw figure using the mouse and post message explanation in the comment box that ampere simultaneously with the white board for other users to view . It is multi-users java chat and drawing program and so the systems that are connected must be enabled to download Java applets.

Conclusion:

Services are the heart of any kind of Library. Web based library services is a trend. Libraries are taking full advantages of internet and web facilities. They are remarkable changing their mode of provision of services. Users are also very happy by getting the services through web. They can save their time and harassment from not getting the information. The western countries have gone far miles than developing and underdeveloped countries. This new mode of service is highly effective in special libraries rather than academic libraries. In our country we are for backward in this matter. Though we are thinking a lot but in practical it is very difficult to apply. Our national policy is there is no intension of implementation. Here is no infrastructure at all to implementation web based library services. Various networking systems in our country is simply failed due to the lack of good will. effort and ego problem of big libraries. But still we hope we will enable to overcome these entire problems and to meet these challenges the library professionals may play a leadership role in providing better Web base library services facilities to their current techno savvy users.

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